

Supplementary Material 1: From Concourse to Q-Set

- a. Cat management study: full concourse, plus stages of reduction and refinement to reach final Q set.
- b. Ammunition study: themes and sub-themes in concourse development

The final Q set for each study can be found in the factor arrays provided in Supplementary Material 6.

They should be outside. They should have... they should be able to have the sun shining on their faces, to explore on grass, to catch insects, to catch mice	2	Cats should be able to have the sun shining on their faces, to explore grass, to catch insects and mice.	Specified 'cats' rather than 'they' and trimmed	Cats should be able to have the sun shining on their faces, to explore grass, to catch insects and mice.		Cats should be able to have the sun shining on their faces, to explore grass, to catch insects and mice.		Cats should be able to have the sun shining on their faces, to explore grass, to hunt insects and mice	Catch adds extra element - change to hunt	Cats should be able to have the sun shining on their faces, to explore grass, to hunt insects and mice	
I worry about them being stolen, getting locked in somewhere, being run over more than anything.	3	I worry about roaming cats being stolen, getting lost, or being run over.	Trimmed, exchanged 'locked in' for more general 'lost'	I worry about roaming cats being lost or stolen; AND I worry about roaming cats being run over	Split into two statements	I worry about roaming cats being lost, stolen or killed by traffic	Recombined for simplicity, clarified	I worry about roaming cats being lost, stolen or killed by traffic		I worry about roaming cats being lost, stolen or killed by traffic	
If I could save anything I will.	3	If I can save any prey brought home I will.	Specified 'prey' brought home	If I can save any prey brought home I will.		If I can rescue the prey my cats bring home, I do.	Reworded to reflect broader sentiment	If my cat brought prey home and I could rescue it, I would	Some cats don't hunt... (JS)	If my cat brought prey home and I could rescue it, I would	
It's not nice that they catch stuff but it's natural for them	3	It's not nice that cats catch things	REMOVED - Catch things could be misconstrued - disease								
	3	It's natural for cats to catch things	REMOVED - Catch things could be								

			misconstrued - disease								
they've got more right, I think to be there than the cat.	3	Wildlife has more right to be outdoors than cats	Specified that wildlife was topic here	Wildlife has more right to be outdoors than cats		Wildlife has more of a right to life than a cat has the right to be outdoors	Clarified sentiment	Wildlife has more of a right to life than a cat has the right to be outdoors		Wildlife has more of a right to life than a cat has the right to be outdoors	
Have them microchipped, wouldn't you say. R: Well, yes. R2: If they get lost they can be found.	3	Owners should have cats microchipped	REMOVED - peripheral issue								
I don't agree with this biscuit diets. R: No. R2: Because it's not natural for them, because they won't eat biscuits in the wild	3	I don't agree with biscuit diets because it's not natural for them	REMOVED - Two clauses - 1) don't agree, 2) reasoning; peripheral								
R: The nature of the cat is difficult to know where they go.	3	The nature of cats makes it difficult to know where they go	REMOVED - uncertain what this adds								

I had them growing up	4	I had cats growing up	REMOVED - all 'why people have cats' to refine topics								
I just like having them around really	4	I just like having cats around	REMOVED - all 'why people have cats' to refine topics								
I like their independence	4	I like cats' independence	REMOVED - all 'why people have cats' to refine topics								
for me, they should be allowed to come and go as they please.	4	Cats should be allowed to come and go as they please	Specified 'cats'		REMOVED (later reinstated as 'cats should have free access to both the house and the outdoors')						
I still don't think it's natural to keep a cat indoors.	4	I don't think it's natural to keep a cat indoors	REMOVED - similar to other statements								
I would imagine outdoors is more their natural environment than indoors	4	Outdoors is more cats' natural environment than indoors	REMOVED - covered by other statements								

really and, yeah, he spends a lot of time outdoors.											
I didn't want him to bring in animals or, you know, birds or whatever. I don't like it. I get cross with him.	4	I get cross with my cat for bringing in animals.	Shortened and simplified	I get cross with my cat for bringing in animals.		I would be cross with my cat for bringing in animals	Broadened to apply to those whose cats don't hunt	If my cat brought in animals, I would feel cross	Disagreed with this but also said would tell cat off for bringing in animals (presumably in effort to train) - so could be better phrased? (DF) Thought about changing to 'tell off' but then this is more about a behaviour - and am more interested in the feeling?		REMOVED: largely covered by "I would be unhappy if my cat caused any animal to suffer"
it's difficult, isn't it, because they catch things to eat, don't they? That's the	4	Cats catch things to eat, but it's not like my cat is hungry.	REMOVED - similar to another statement and less clear								

whole idea, but it's not like he's hungry because I don't starve him.											
I think they'd need to be... unless you specifically wanted to breed from them I think they should be neutered.	4	Unless you specifically want to breed from them I think cats should be neutered.	REMOVED - peripheral issue								
how can you be responsible for your cat, because they're so independent, aren't they? I don't think you can be.	4	I don't think you can be responsible for your cat because they're so independent .	REMOVED - two clauses								
I don't think you can be responsible for it like you can a dog really.	4	I don't think you can be responsible for a cat like you can for a dog.	REMOVED - covered by broader responsibility statement								
I can imagine if you're not a cat owner or a cat lover if your neighbour's cats were coming into your	4	I can imagine if you're not a cat owner or a cat lover and your neighbour's cats were	REMOVED - peripheral issue								

garden and toileting then that would be pretty annoying.		coming into your garden and toileting, that would be pretty annoying.									
I suppose it's my responsibility really to stop him going in there. But I wouldn't... so that goes against the letting them roam and do what they want to do, doesn't it?	4	It's my responsibility to stop my cat going in other people's properties.	REMOVED - peripheral issue								
I think ultimately it's my responsibility. It's my animal, it should be my responsibility.	4	Ultimately, my cat is my animal and should be my responsibility.	REMOVED - covered by responsibility statement later								
R: But then for me I'm denying him his natural instincts, whatever.	4	Restricting roaming is denying my cat their natural instincts.	Clarified and provided context		REMOVED (covered by positive statements about outdoor access)						

he's not bringing in hoards of dead things.	4	My cat doesn't bring in hoards of dead things.	REMOVED - factual, can be covered in survey								
I didn't think about [hunting] really much when I thought about having another cat.	4	I didn't think about hunting much when I thought about getting a cat.	Broadened and clarified	I didn't think about hunting much when I thought about getting a cat.		When I got a cat, I didn't really think about whether it would hunt	Reworded for clarity	When I got a cat, I didn't really think about whether it would hunt		When I got a cat, I didn't really think about whether it would hunt	
You know when they do go out in traffic and goodness knows what. You know, you've just got to take that risk.	5	You've just got to take the risk that cats might go out in traffic.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
Thomas goes into the house next door. I: Oh, right. Do they mind? R: No, they welcome him. They seem to like him there.	5	My neighbours welcome my cats on their property.	REMOVED - peripheral								
I still feel a bit cross with them and yet we know that, you know, they bring it in because it's the	5	Cats bring prey in as a trophy or present for their owners	Shortened and simplified	Cats bring prey in as a trophy or present for their owners		Cats that bring in prey do so as a present for their owners	Amended to recognise that not all cats return prey	Cats that bring in prey do so as a present for their owners		Cats that bring in prey do so as a present for their owners	

trophy and they want us to know how clever they are and this is a present for you.											
even after all these thousands of years that, sort of, semi feral instinct to be out there is still there.	5	Even after thousands of years, cats' semi-feral instinct to be out there is still there.	REMOVED - covered by other statements								
Some cats don't want to go outdoors.	6	Some cats don't want to go outdoors.		Some cats don't want to go outdoors.		Some cats don't want to go outdoors		Some cats would prefer to be indoors	Invert to make positive statement	Some cats would prefer to be indoors	
I can't imagine being trapped inside gives a cat the stimulation it needs.	6	I can't imagine being inside gives a cat the stimulation it needs.	Removed 'trapped' (less sensational, same sentiment)	I can't imagine being inside gives a cat the stimulation it needs.		I can't imagine being inside gives a cat the stimulation it needs.		I am concerned that being kept inside doesn't give cats the stimulation they need	Clarified sentiment	I am concerned that being kept inside doesn't give cats the stimulation they need	
It's annoying when she brings stuff in and kills it and then just plays with it, doesn't eat it.	6	It's annoying when my cat brings stuff in and then just plays with it, and doesn't eat it.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								

<p>You know full well what cats are like when you get a cat, so anybody that keeps them in for that, I also find annoying. Don't get a cat, basically.</p>	6	<p>People who would keep a cat in to prevent hunting shouldn't get a cat.</p>	Shortened		REMOVED in this form	<p>ADDED: People should keep cats inside to stop them hunting</p>	<p>Simpler, positively phrased means to find views on same issue</p>	<p>Cats should be kept inside to stop them hunting</p>	<p>Made less judgemental / normative towards other people while retaining sentiment</p>	<p>Cats should be kept inside to stop them hunting</p>	
<p>I think it's up to them to take precautions to protect whatever it is, because if it's a cat it might be a fox. No-one's responsible for that.</p>	6	<p>It's up to other people to take precautions to protect their property, because if it's a cat it might be a fox. No-one is responsible for that.</p>	REMOVED - peripheral issue								
<p>I mean what harm is Myrtle going to do when there's millions of cats, that's all I can think.</p>	6	<p>There are millions of cats; one isn't going to do much harm to wildlife.</p>	Shortened and broadened	<p>One cat alone isn't going to do much harm to wildlife.</p>	Simplified	<p>One cat can't do much harm to wildlife by itself</p>	Clarified	<p>One cat can't do much harm to wildlife by itself</p>		<p>One cat can't do much harm to wildlife by itself</p>	
<p>I have to say I don't like the idea of keeping cats indoors</p>	7	<p>I don't like the idea of keeping cats indoors</p>	REMOVED - covered by another statement								

when I see them outside, I realise how important that is to them, to be out and exploring and also finding like grass or whatever herbs they might want to eat.	7	When I see cats outside, I realise how important it is to them.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
it's something about the kind of uncaring nature and I know that they don't mean it like that but it's about this uncaring nature isn't it? Well I'm not interested in that anymore.	7	I don't like cats' uncaring nature towards their prey.	Shortened and simplified	I don't like cats' uncaring nature towards their prey.		I don't like cats' uncaring nature towards their prey.		Cats are cruel to their prey	Perceived as similar to another statement (about suffering) (DF)	Cats are cruel to their prey	
let's be honest there are too many cats in the world and they can reproduce at a most alarming rate.	7	There are too many cats in the world and they can reproduce at a most alarming rate.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								

there's lots of things that are affecting wildlife, certainly can't blame it primarily on a cat, can you?	7	There's lots of things affecting wildlife, you can't blame it primarily on a cat.	Shortened	There's lots of things affecting wildlife, you can't blame it primarily on cats.	Reworded for clarity	You can't blame any declines in wildlife primarily on cats	Reworded again for clarity and to make one clause	Any declines in wildlife cannot be blamed primarily on cats	"Any" changes meaning slightly here - rephrased (SLC)	Any declines in wildlife cannot be blamed primarily on cats	
if we've ever had a kitten, I do keep it in for the majority of its first year.	8	I keep a kitten in for the majority of its first year.	REMOVED - too specific								
cats are independent by nature and they'll do exactly what they like. In some ways, that's why we like them, because they do that.	8	I like cats because they are independent and will do exactly what they like	REMOVED - all 'why people have cats' to refine topics								
Don't like it at all, particularly with the birds because they really are ... I: Particularly birds, hmm. R: I can understand people being very anti-cats because of that.	8	I don't like cats hunting at all, and I can understand people being very anti-cat because of that.	Shortened and broadened	I can understand people being very anti-cat because of their hunting behaviour.	Reworded for clarity and to removed negative	I can understand some people being anti-cat because of their hunting behaviour.	Softened language	I can understand some people being anti-cat because of their hunting behaviour.		I can understand some people being anti-cat because of their hunting behaviour.	

for a start, domesticated animals aren't natural wild animals, they don't exist outside our creating them in a way.	9	Domestic cats aren't natural, wild animals	REMOVED - incorporated one wildness ref into another statement								
if I kept them in and they didn't want to be in, then that would be ... it'd be putting them in a stressful situation	9	If I kept cats in and they didn't want to be in, I'd be putting them in a stressful situation.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
I don't think it's cat's fault they're not like I think I'll go murder a bird today. And I think sometimes we'll tend to say, they're vicious, they're violent, they're hunting, yeah of course they are because that's what they are	9	It's not a cat's fault they're vicious, violent, or hunting: that's what they are.	REMOVED - too many clauses, doesn't tell us much								

you'll read the incredible figure of how many wild creatures that cats will kill and it, to a large extent, that's because we've got a huge population of cats	9	Cats will kill an incredible number of wild creatures because we've got a huge population of cats	Shortened and simplified	Cats will kill an incredible number of wild creatures because we've got a huge population of cats		Cats kill a huge number of wild animals because there's a huge population of cats	Clarified	There are too many cats in this country	Two ways to disagree - (1) that cats kill a lot and (2) that there's a huge population. Replaced with statement about population suggested by pilot participant	There are too many cats in this country	
if you breed too many of a predator then you will have an imbalance in any population.	9	If you breed too many of a predator then you will have an imbalance in any population.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
if you are an owner or you are ... have responsibility for this particular animal, then that extends to whatever they do.	9	If you are an owner or you have responsibility for this particular animal, then that extends to whatever they do.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								

I think I'm a little uncomfortable with the idea of cats being kept inside but I guess they do adapt.	10	I'm a little uncomfortable with the idea of cats being kept inside, but I guess they adapt	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
We're making them into these indoor cats because it suits us,	10	We're making cats into indoor animals because it suits us	REMOVED - uncertain sentiment								
the cat family they all originate from outdoors and it feels kind of wrong to have cats (unclear 29:02) and not allow them access to the outside.	10	The cat family all originate from outdoors and it feels kind of wrong to not allow them access to the outside.	REMOVED - wildness topic								
I love birds but it's just what cats do.	10	I love animals, but hunting is just what cats do.	Broadened and clarified	I love animals, but hunting is just what cats do.		I love wildlife, but hunting is just what cats do.	Broadened to wildlife	I love wildlife, but hunting is just what cats do.		I love wildlife, but hunting is just what cats do.	
I don't think his hunting is ... he's prolific but I don't think it's frequent	10	My cat hunts, but I don't think it's frequent enough to	REMOVED - depends on cat hunting								

enough to have an effect.		have an effect on wildlife.									
if you spend enough time with your pet, that that can possibly make a difference.	11	If you spend enough time with your cat, that can make a difference to the amount it hunts.		If you spend enough time with your cat, it can make a difference to the amount it hunts.		If you spend enough time with your cat, it can make a difference to the amount it hunts.		If you spend enough time with your cat, it can make a difference to the amount it hunts.		If you spend enough time with your cat, it can make a difference to the amount it hunts.	
I don't like it at all because we know the bird population in the gardens is reduced hugely.	12	I don't like hunting behaviour at all because we know the bird population in gardens is reduced hugely.	Clarified	I don't like cats hunting because garden bird populations have been reduced hugely.	Re-worded for clarity	I don't like cats hunting because I am worried about garden bird populations	Reworded to rely less on belief, reflect concern	I worry about the effect of cats hunting on garden bird populations	Two ways to disagree - reworded	I worry about the effect of cats hunting on garden bird populations	
Cats are killing off some of the birds aren't they... I think there's no question that the cats must be responsible for a fair bit.	12	There's no question that cats must be responsible for killing off some of the birds.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
I am very aware of that and try to stop them catching birds	12	I try to stop my cats catching		I try to stop my cats catching		I try to stop my cats catching birds	Simplified		REMOVED - Some cats don't hunt... (JS) +		

when I can really.		birds when I can.		birds when I can.					covered by two other statements combined		
I believe a cat should be outdoor but bring them in at night if you wish.	13	A cat should be outdoor, but bring them in at night if you wish.	Shortened	A cat should be outdoor, but bring them in at night if you wish.		Cats should be allowed out but its OK to keep them in at night	Reworded for clarity	Cats should be allowed out but its OK to keep them in at night		Cats should be allowed out but its OK to keep them in at night	
I know it's instinct but it does annoy you because you know they're not hungry	13	Hunting annoys me because I know they're not hungry	Shortened	Hunting annoys me because I know they're not hungry		Hunting by cats annoys me because I know they're not hungry.	Clarified topic = cats	Hunting by cats annoys me because I know they're not hungry.		Hunting by cats annoys me because I know they're not hungry.	
You don't keep an indoor lion do you. I just think they're wild animals at the end of the day.	13	You don't keep an indoor lion; I just think they're wild animals at the end of the day.	REMOVED - wildness topic								
I mean she would prefer a bowl of food to me.	13	My cat would prefer a bowl of food to me.	REMOVED - uncertain sentiment								
That's fine, that's great, as long as the owner's providing a lot of enrichment	14	Keeping cats indoors is fine as long as the owner's providing a	Clarified and provided context	Keeping cats indoors is fine as long as the owner's providing a		Keeping cats indoors is fine as long as the owner provides a lot of stimulation	Simplified term	Choosing to keep cats indoors is fine as long as the owner provides a	Some cats have to be kept indoors (e.g. FIV) (JS)	Choosing to keep cats indoors is fine as long as the owner provides a	

		lot of enrichment.		lot of enrichment.				lot of stimulation		lot of stimulation	
I can't necessarily control what my cat does all the time. So, other people have to consider that as well,	14	I can't necessarily control what my cat does all the time; other people have to consider that as well.	REMOVED - multiple clauses, complex sentiment								
I like them because you get that connection with a wild animal as well.	14	I like cats because you get that connection with a wild animal as well.	REMOVED - reasons for keeping cats and wildness both reduced								
we've never thought of getting a collar for him because some of them are dangerous	14	Collars are a bit dangerous		Collars are dangerous	Broadened	Colars are dangerous for cats	Specified what they are dangerous for	Collars can be dangerous for cats	(1) Include 'can be' - less definite but some are, some aren't - makes easier to answer. Plus 'I am concerned that...' so less factual? (SLC) (2)	Collars can be dangerous for cats	

									Does this apply to all collars or just non-safety ones? Do we need to specify 'all' or 'buckled'? (JS)		
Why is it that you have them indoors? R: Because we live near the prom. We are just around behind the prom. I: This road? R: Yes. I: Okay, so it is for their safety really? R: Yes.	15	Keeping cats indoors keeps them safe	Re-written to reflect sentiment	Keeping cats indoors keeps them safe		Keeping cats indoors keeps them safe		Keeping cats indoors keeps them safe	Unclear if this is all the time or not? (JS) - decided to keep broad	Keeping cats indoors keeps them safe	
A cat is an outdoor animal.	16	A cat is an outdoor animal		A cat is an outdoor animal		Cats do not belong in the house	Made clearer (outdoor ONLY, not just outdoor)			Cats do not belong in the house	
I do want them hunting on the farm, keeping the vermin down.	16	I want cats to be hunting and keeping the vermin down.	Clarified and broadened	I want cats to be hunting and keeping the vermin down.		I want cats to be hunting and keeping the vermin down.		I want cats to be hunting and keeping the vermin down.		I want cats to be hunting and keeping the vermin down.	

[Hunting is] the least attractive side of cat ownership I think.	17	Hunting is the least attractive side of cat ownership.		Hunting is the least attractive side of cat ownership.		Their hunting is the least attractive aspect of cat ownership.	Reworded for clarity	Their hunting is the least attractive aspect of cat ownership.		Their hunting is the least attractive aspect of cat ownership.	
I thought well that's a good thing, she's out there, doing a bit of hunting. You know, she's feeling comfortable, relaxed and safe.	17	I think it's a good thing that my cat is out there hunting, because it means they're feeling comfortable, relaxed and safe.		I think it's a good thing that my cat is out there hunting, because it means they're relaxed and happy enough to behave normally.	Reworded for sentiment	Hunting is a good sign because it shows that cats are comfortable and behaving normally.	Broadened and clarified	Hunting is a good sign because it shows that cats are comfortable and behaving normally		Hunting is a good sign because it shows that cats are comfortable and behaving normally	
cat owners should be minding their cats and checking where they're going a bit, if they can, and you know, if they're annoying the neighbours try and do something about that	17	Cat owners should be minding their cats and checking where they're going, if they can.	REMOVED - responsibility covered elsewhere								

	17	If cats are annoying the neighbours, owners should try and do something about it	REMOVED - peripheral issue								
And also making sure all their inoculations and things are up to date – check ups and all that.	17	Owners should make sure all their cats' inoculations are up to date.	REMOVED - peripheral issue								
I hate the thought of a bird being caught.	17	I hate the thought of a bird being caught by a cat.		I hate the thought of a bird being caught by a cat.		I hate the thought of a bird being caught by a cat.			REMOVED: covered by a combination of two other statements		
they don't let the cats out. Because they are these pedigree...	17	I don't let the cats out because they are pedigrees.	REMOVED - can be covered in survey								
they kill birds and you can't say, no, they don't because obviously they do. But then... you know, I suppose, it's one of their... not downsides,	18	Cats kill birds, but that is one of the character traits you take on when you own a cat.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								

<p>but one of their character traits that you take on when you own a cat. You have to accept it and you have to manage it if you can.</p>											
	18	<p>You have to accept hunting, and you have to manage it if you can.</p>	<p>REMOVED - covered by other statements</p>								
<p>We've got someone in our family that has, you know, got an indoor cat, but it's... I would say they are stimulated quite a lot and they're used to it and maybe if you're born into that world that's what you get used to. But I always think it's a shame.</p>	18	<p>Cats brought up indoors get used to it.</p>	<p>Shortened</p>	<p>Cats brought up indoors get used to it.</p>		<p>Cats that are brought up indoors are used to it</p>	<p>Reworded for clarity</p>	<p>Cats that are brought up indoors are used to it</p>		<p>Cats that are brought up indoors are used to it</p>	

I've always been brought up with you keep the cats in at night so they don't hunt.	18	If you keep cats in at night they won't hunt as much	Shortened, sentiment retained	If you keep cats in at night they won't hunt as much		If you keep cats in at night they won't catch as much	Specified 'catch' rather than hunt	If you keep cats in at night they won't catch as much		If you keep cats in at night they won't catch as much	
I don't like to see anything suffering to be honest, no matter what it is, and when it's dead it's still upsetting because that poor little creature didn't have much of a chance	18	I don't like to see anything suffering, no matter what it is.	Shortened	I don't like to see anything suffering, no matter what it is.		I would be unhappy if my cat caused any animal to suffer	Reworded for clarity and specificity	I would be unhappy if my cat caused any animal to suffer		I would be unhappy if my cat caused any animal to suffer	
they've got their cats out in the run and they don't go in the house. They live outside.	18	I keep cats in a run and they don't go in the house.	REMOVED - can be covered in survey								
[when cats indoors] I felt really guilty, so guilty and I just didn't want to be playing with them all the time.	19	I feel guilty about keeping my cats indoors.	REMOVED - covered by other statements								

	19	I don't want to be playing with my cats all the time.		I don't want to be playing with my cat all the time		I don't want to have to spend time playing with the cat	Reworded for clarity	I don't want to have to spend time playing with the cat		I don't want to have to spend time playing with the cat	
ours are not very quick and they've never really caught anything.	19	My cat has never really caught anything.	REMOVED - can be covered in survey								
He is quite prolific. R: Yes, he is, yes. He is a real hunter.	19	My cat is quite prolific; a real hunter.	REMOVED - can be covered in survey								
I don't like it at all. I: You don't like it? Why don't you like it? R: Well I mean because I love birds and I love all other animals basically	20	I don't like my cat hunting because I love birds and all other animals.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
If I was really concerned about I wouldn't have had cats. I know that's what they do.	20	If I was really concerned about cats hunting I wouldn't have had cats.	Shortened	If I was really concerned about cats hunting I wouldn't have had cats.		If I was really concerned about cats hunting I wouldn't have had cats.			REMOVED: Tricky to understand - two things to disagree with (NC) + not sure adds much insight.		

Everything's so domesticated here that there's not just packs of wild dogs or cats roaming around causing havoc in the countryside.	21	Everything is so domesticated in the UK; there's not wild cats roaming around causing havoc in the countryside.	REMOVED - wildness topic								
I'm not bothered by it at all	22	I'm not bothered by my cat hunting at all.		I'm not bothered by my cat hunting at all.		I'm not bothered by my cat hunting.	Simplified	Cats hunting doesn't bother me	Some cats don't hunt (JS)	Cats hunting doesn't bother me	
I don't mind if they're going further. I'd almost probably prefer that they have a little adventure but I don't think they do.	22	I don't mind my cats roaming; I'd almost prefer that they have a little adventure.	REMOVED - covered by other statements								
If they hunt then that's what they should do.	22	If cats hunt then that's what they should be allowed do.	REMOVED - vague								
I wouldn't want the smell of a cat litter tray.	22	I wouldn't want the smell of a cat litter tray.	REMOVED - peripheral issue								

If you've got a nervous cat that's used to being indoors and happy indoors fair enough.	23	If you've got a cat that's happy indoors fair enough.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
I would prefer not to have birds. R1: You like the wild birds. R2: Yeah I do,	23	I would prefer not to have birds brought in; I like wild birds.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
he's great for catching spiders and I don't like spiders.	23	Cats are great for catching spiders	Simplified	Cats are great for catching spiders			REMOVED - too specific				
they're keeping the mice population down.	23	Cats help to keep rat and mouse populations down	Clarified sentiment	Cats help to keep rat and mouse populations down	Cats help to keep rodent populations down	Simplified	Cats help to keep rodent populations down			Cats help to keep rodent populations down	
They've got a right to roam wherever like a wild animal.	23	Cats should have the right to roam wherever, like a wild animal.	Made normative	Cats should have the right to roam wherever, like a wild animal.	Cats should have the right to roam like a wild animal.	Simplified	Cats should have the right to roam where they please, like a wild animal	Unclear how wild cats would behave (JS) - clarified, reintroduced some of earlier sentiment		Cats should have the right to roam where they please, like a wild animal	
. You can't stop a cat from peeing or	23	You can't stop a cat from peeing or pooping in	REMOVED - peripheral issue								

pooing in their garden.		someone's garden.									
it's what cats do so you've got to put up with it.	24	Hunting is what cats do so you've got to put up with it.	Merged with a another statement -- > "I love wildlife, but hunting is just what cats do"								
I didn't like it when Pebs used to bring in stuff in because you'd find it hidden all over the place.	24	I don't like it when cats bring stuff in because you find it hidden all over the place.	REMOVED - too specific								
you can't train a cat like you can train a dog.	24	You can't train a cat like you can train a dog.	REMOVED - uncertain what this adds								
I think they are still basically a wild animal.	24	I think cats are still basically a wild animal.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								

<p>we've just had the Cats Protection newsletter and there's a huge incidence of cats being shot by air guns now. I: Yeah and they're poisoning. R2: And poisoning them. I: Yeah. R1: I mean a friend of ours had his cat or their cat poisoned with antifreeze. I: That does happen. R1: You hear of it going on and I think well these two are safe from that.</p>	<p>24</p>	<p>Roaming cats are at risk from being shot by air guns and poisoned.</p>		<p>Roaming cats are at risk from being shot by air guns or poisoned.</p>		<p>Roaming cats are at risk of being deliberately hurt by people.</p>	<p>Broadened to reflect wider sentiment</p>	<p>I am concerned that roaming cats are at risk of being deliberately hurt by people</p>	<p>Precede with "I am concerned that..." to make perspective - fits with other roaming risks (SLC)</p>	<p>I worry that roaming cats are at risk of being deliberately hurt by people</p>	<p>Rephrased to match other 'I worry' statements</p>
<p>if you let it go outside there's always the risk of it getting run over.</p>	<p>25</p>	<p>If you let your cat go outside there's always a risk of it getting run over.</p>	<p>REMOVED - incorporated into another statement</p>								

You can't stop them.	25	You can't stop cats hunting.	Clarified	You can't stop cats hunting.		You can't stop cats hunting.		"It's impossible for owners to prevent cats hunting" AND/OR "Owners shouldn't stop their cats hunting"	Can be read two ways (NC)	Owners can't stop their cats hunting	
I think it's completely against a cat's nature to keep a cat indoors like that.	25	I think it's completely against a cat's nature to keep it indoors.	REMOVED - Later incorporated into 'keeping cats indoors is cruel')								
I know [hunting is] a cat's nature but it's just so cruel	25	I know hunting is a cat's nature, but it's just so cruel.	Combined with another statement -- > Cats are cruel to their prey								
there's the risk of them getting knocked down, that's the main sort of thing that I think about, or getting lost when going outside but I think the quality of life	26	I think about the risk of my cat getting knocked down, or getting lost, but I think the quality of life when going outside		I think about the risk of my cat getting knocked down, or getting lost, but I think the quality of life when going outside		The benefits to my cat of going outside outweigh the risks of them getting injured or lost	Broadened and simplified	The benefits to cats of going outside outweigh the risks of them getting injured or lost	Some cats don't go outside (SLC)	The benefits to cats of going outside outweigh the risks of them getting injured or lost	

outweighs that risk, for me		outweighs that risk		outweighs that risk							
[Hunting is] more of a nuisance than anything else really.	26	Hunting behaviour is more of a nuisance than anything else.		Hunting behaviour is more of a nuisance than anything else.		Cats hunting is just a nuisance	Reworded for clarity	Cats hunting is just a nuisance		Cats hunting is just a nuisance	
[I have a friend who] is frustrated by the fact that cat owners don't have to take responsibility and I do understand that and I think it's a difficult one.	26	People are frustrated by the fact that cat owners don't have to take responsibility.	REMOVED - limited coverage of responsibility								

<p>the worst thing, certainly with him, is the hunting because obviously that's a bit gross</p>	<p>26</p>	<p>Cats bringing prey home is a bit gross</p>	<p>Shortened and simplified</p>	<p>Cats bringing prey home is a bit gross</p>		<p>Cats bringing prey home is gross</p>	<p>Simplified</p>	<p>Having to deal with prey that cats bring home is disgusting</p>	<p>Put off by use of term gross which felt childish. More likely to agree if more neutral. Also, should probably specify that it is dealing with the prey that is gross, not the cats' bringing it in</p>	<p>Having to deal with prey that cats bring home is disgusting</p>	
<p>if there was real statistics that say, 'These are now endangered because of cats,' then I would take much more seriously getting a collar and a bell and just finding a way to really make that work, or whatever, or maybe that should be legislated or</p>	<p>26</p>	<p>If there were statistics saying 'this species is now endangered because of cats', then I would take managing my cat's hunting behaviour much more seriously.</p>	<p>Shortened and simplified</p>	<p>If there were statistics saying 'this species is now endangered because of cats', then I would take managing my cat's hunting behaviour much more seriously.</p>		<p>If there was scientific evidence saying 'this species is endangered because of cats', then I would take managing my cat's hunting behaviour much more seriously.</p>	<p>Specified evidence rather than statistics <i>per se</i></p>	<p>If there was scientific evidence saying 'this species is endangered because of cats', then I would take managing my cat's hunting behaviour much more seriously.</p>		<p>If there was scientific evidence saying 'this species is endangered because of cats', then I would take managing my cat's hunting behaviour much more seriously</p>	

something, you know, if there was a real problem.											
it's not something that I've ever ... I: Come across really. R: Not that I've come across in a way that I've seriously thought, no.	26	The potential for cats to effect wildlife is not something I've ever seriously thought about.	Clarified sentiment	The potential for cats' hunting to affect wildlife is not something I've ever seriously thought about.		I've never seriously thought about whether cats affect wildlife populations	Reworded for clarity	I've never seriously thought about whether cats affect wildlife populations		I've never seriously thought about whether cats affect wildlife populations	
People think that foxes will attack cats but they won't.	27	Foxes will attack cats.	Reversed negative	Foxes will attack cats.		Foxes will attack cats that are out at night	Specified when cats might be at risk	I worry that foxes will attack cats that are out at night	Make 'I worry that' so can ID if a concern rather than a belief? (NC)	I worry that foxes will attack cats that are out at night	

In fact more of my friends are in America. So a lot of them were like no we keep our cat inside, it's much safer. You've got to be very careful with the traffic and diseases they could pick up and all kinds of things.	28	You've got to be very careful with diseases roaming cats could pick up.	Specified to disease and shortened	You've got to be very careful with diseases roaming cats could pick up.		I worry about diseases that roaming cats could pick up.	Reworded to reflect sentiment	I worry about diseases that roaming cats could pick up.		I worry about diseases that roaming cats could pick up.	
We'd be upset if she was doing a lot of hunting, it really might change our minds about keeping a cat if we had a cat that was constantly killing things.	28	I'd be upset if my cat did a lot of hunting.		I'd be upset if my cat did a lot of hunting.		I'd be upset if my cat killed a lot of wildlife	Specified why would be upset		REMOVED: Scale element not that clear (DF); now very similar to 50		
	28	I might change my mind about keeping a cat if it was constantly killing things.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								

The only way around that where things are vulnerable is to no allow them to have cats.	29	The only option where there is vulnerable wildlife is to not allow people to have cats.		The only option where there is vulnerable wildlife is to not allow people to have cats.		Where there is vulnerable wildlife, people should not be allowed to have cats	Reworded for clarity	Where there is vulnerable wildlife, people should not be allowed to have cats		Where there is vulnerable wildlife, people should not be allowed to have cats	
She wouldn't like it if I just shut her out. In fact she gets stressed.	29	My cat wouldn't like it if I shut it out; it would be stressed.	REMOVED - too specific								
I think you can take personal responsibility to a point, when you can.	29	I think you can take personal responsibility for you cat to a point.	REMOVED (but later covered by another statement)								
it's not that the dead thing worries me it is purely that I didn't want him to be destroying all the birds	29	I'm not worried by dead things, but I don't want my cat to be destroying all the birds.		I'm not worried by dead things, but I don't want my cat to be destroying all the birds.		I don't mind dead things as such, but I don't want my cat to kill lots of birds.	Reworded for clarity	I would only really be concerned about cats hunting if they were catching birds	Tricky to understand - two things to disagree with (NC) + not sure adds much insight - created new, more useful statement	I would only really be concerned about cats hunting if they were catching birds	
I would feel sad myself I think to have a cat that was so domesticated	30	I would feel sad to have a cat that was so domesticate	REMOVED - wildness topic								

that it can't go outside, as we've discussed		d it couldn't go outside.									
I had a cat who was catching birds and I knew they were species that were declining I probably would feel bad about that actually.	30	If I had a cat who was catching birds and I knew they were a species that was declining, I would feel bad about that.		If I had a cat who was catching birds and I knew they were a species that was declining, I would feel bad about that.			REMOVED - covered by another statement				
I would definitely want to have a cat who was both indoor and outdoor or if it was just purely where we lived then outdoor but no I wouldn't want that because I would want them to come inside.	30	I wouldn't want to have an outdoor only cat because I would want it to come inside.		I want a cat that comes inside, so I wouldn't want an outdoor-only cat	Reworded so positive first	I want a cat that comes inside, so I wouldn't want an outdoor-only cat		I want a cat that comes inside, so I wouldn't want an outdoor-only cat		I want a cat that comes inside, so I wouldn't want an outdoor-only cat	

<p>I was quite loath to do the neutering but it was a condition of the animal sanctuary... I felt more like I was taking his manhood, or their manhood, away.</p>	<p>31</p>	<p>I don't like neutering male cats as it feels like taking their manhood away.</p>	<p>REMOVED - peripheral issue</p>								
<p>How do you feel about that? R: Proud actually.</p>	<p>31</p>	<p>I am proud of my cat for hunting.</p>		<p>I am proud of my cat for hunting.</p>		<p>I am proud of my cat for hunting.</p>		<p>I would be proud of my cat for hunting</p>	<p>Not all cats hunt - made more general</p>	<p>I would be proud of my cat for hunting</p>	
<p>vulnerable populations of wildlife. Have you ever thought about that as an issue? R: Well, I've got so many other things to worry about to be honest that no. I: It's not up there. R: It's not something I worry about, no. No, maybe that's irresponsible, but... it doesn't really cross my mind.</p>	<p>31</p>	<p>Cats hunting wildlife is not something I worry about.</p>	<p>REMOVED - covered by another statement</p>								

I don't really like mice and voles so I don't think I mind.	32	I don't really like rodents so I don't mind cats hunting them.		I don't mind cats hunting rodents.	Simplified	I don't mind cats hunting rodents.		I have no problem with cats hunting rodents	Attempted to make more positive...		REMOVED: covered by other rodent statement and not bothered by hunting
I would see it as a restriction to make them stay. I: What is it about being able to go outside that you think is important? R: To be able to do their natural behaviours.	33	I would see it as a restriction to make cats stay indoors.	REMOVED - later covered by 'keeping cats indoors is cruel'								
they have to eat meat. They don't have to hunt.	33	Cats have to eat meat, but they don't have to hunt.		Cats have to eat meat, but they don't have to hunt.		Cats have to hunt to get the meat they need	Inverted to make positive		REMOVED: Placed at +6 because 'patently untrue' - could confound more important elements, i.e. perspectives ? Alternatively could rephrase as "Wild-caught		

									food is better for cats' health than pet food" (JB)		
they're not a toy, they are an animal and they deserve to be respected and looked after because they are dependent on us	34	Cats deserve to be respected and looked after because they are dependent on us.	REMOVED - vague								
I would never say that you have to keep your cat in or your have to keep your cat out. I know a lot of people that put their cats out at night.	34	I would never say that you have to keep your cat in or have to keep your cat out.			REMOVED - later incorporated in another statement						

the thing that hit us so hard when Jasper was killed was not just because we'd lost jasper but because we hadn't been able to look after him. I mean you can't stop them wandering but he had died because ... there was nothing we could do about it but we hadn't prevented it happening.	34	If my cat was killed when roaming, I would be upset that I hadn't prevented it happening.		If my cat was killed when roaming, I would be upset that I hadn't prevented it happening.		If my cat was killed when roaming, I would feel guilty that I hadn't prevented it.	Reworded to clarify sentiment	If my cat was killed when roaming, I would feel guilty that I hadn't prevented it.		If my cat was killed when roaming, I would feel guilty that I hadn't prevented it.	
I don't like handling dead birds.	34	I don't like handling dead birds.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								
They choose to be with us. If they didn't want to be with us they would be out there. How can you force them?	35	Cats choose to be with us; if they didn't want to be with us they wouldn't be.	REMOVED - uncertain sentiment								

<p>I don't actually mind as long as they have not got maggots all over them.</p>	<p>35</p>	<p>I don't actually mind cats bringing things home as long as they hasn't got maggots all over them.</p>	<p>REMOVED - covered by other statements</p>								
<p>It doesn't bother me. I am not ...I am an animal lover but I do realise there is hunter killing and eating andI am not a vegetarian, I can't talk.</p>	<p>35</p>	<p>Cats hunting doesn't bother me; I am an animal lover but I realise there is hunting, killing and eating.</p>	<p>REMOVED (but later returned as 'Cats hunting doesn't bother me')</p>								
<p>I think it is natural for them to want to go out and experience the world. If they happen to fall foul of it that's nature.</p>	<p>35</p>	<p>I think it is natural for cats to want to go out and experience the world; if they happen to fall foul of it that's nature.</p>		<p>I think it is natural for cats to want to go out and experience the world; if they happen to fall foul of it that's nature.</p>		<p>It is natural for cats to want to go out into the world; if they happen to fall foul of it, that's also natural.</p>	<p>Reworded for clarity</p>	<p>It is natural for cats to want to go out into the world; if they happen to fall foul of it, that's also natural.</p>	<p>Fall foul - tricky if not native speaker (DF) Also questioned this (FB); decided to keep as original wording and captures sentiment well</p>	<p>It is natural for cats to want to go out into the world; if they happen to fall foul of it, that's also natural.</p>	

Responsible owners put collars and a bell round their cat's neck and keep their cats in at night.	Western Daily Press, 19/2/14	Responsible owners put collars and a bell around their cat's neck.		Responsible owners put a collar with a bell around their cat's neck.	Reworded	Responsible owners put a collar with a bell on their cat	Softened language	Belled collars can reduce the amount cats hunt	Can be read as a belief or normative statement (NC)	Belled collars can reduce the amount cats hunt	
It is quite easy to keep cats out of gardens by using lion dung and making sure the birds are kept safe by not planting any low-lying bushes the cats can hide behind when they are after birds.	Western Daily Press, 19/2/14	It is quite easy to keep cats out of gardens.	REMOVED - covered (partially) by another statement, somewhat peripheral								
it's distressing when animals die needlessly but there are far more humanity issues in the world which need addressing before we start on the common moggy.	Gloucestershire Echo, 4/7/15	It's distressing when animals die needlessly.	REMOVED - covered by another statement								

<p>Particularly at this time of year, when there will soon be many young birds fledging, it is vital that cats are either kept indoors or in restricted areas of gardens, which is what I have done with my cat for some time.</p>	<p>North Devon Journal, 15/5/2008</p>	<p>When there are birds fledging cats should be kept indoors or in restricted areas of gardens.</p>		<p>When there are birds fledging cats should be kept indoors or in restricted areas of gardens.</p>		<p>When there are baby birds around, cats should be kept indoors or in restricted areas of gardens.</p>	<p>Simplified language</p>	<p>When there are baby birds around, cats should be kept indoors or in restricted areas of gardens.</p>		<p>When there are baby birds around, cats should be kept indoors or in restricted areas of gardens.</p>	
<p>A cat is only following its natural instincts, it is up to owners to curb this unnecessary slaughter.</p>	<p>North Devon Journal, 15/5/2008</p>	<p>A cat is only following its natural instincts; it is up to owners to curb hunting behaviour.</p>		<p>A cat is only following its natural instincts; it is up to owners to curb hunting behaviour.</p>		<p>It is up to owners to curb their cats' instinct to hunt</p>	<p>Simplified, removed a clause</p>	<p>It is my responsibility, as an owner, to manage my cat's hunting behaviour</p>	<p>Owners have a responsibility to - more explicitly about responsibility? (SLC) - replaced with new statement - curbing natural instinct to hunt sounds harder than 'managing hunting behaviour' - includes suggestion</p>	<p>It is my responsibility, as an owner, to manage my cat's hunting behaviour</p>	

									from pilot, "I do everything I can to minimise the impact of my cat's hunting"		
Having a cat should no longer be the 'easy' option - with many owners letting their cats roam free all day (and some all night!); to cause havoc to our desperately threatened wildlife.	North Devon Journal, 15/5/2008	Letting cats roam free all day and night causes havoc to our desperately threatened wildlife.		Letting cats roam free all day and night causes havoc to our desperately threatened wildlife.		Letting cats roam free causes havoc for our threatened wildlife	Softened language	Letting cats roam free causes havoc for our threatened wildlife		Letting cats roam free causes havoc for our threatened wildlife	
unless something is done to prevent such carnage, the cats could	Grimsby Evening Telegraph, 26/6/2003	Cats could push some of the most vulnerable species to			REMOVED - covered by another statement						

push some of the most vulnerable species to the brink of extinction.		the brink of extinction.									
cat owners should at least: a). Fit a collar with a bell, preferably a sonic one. b). Keep the cats in at night, and c). Provide their cats with toys.	Grimsby Evening Telegraph, 26/6/2003	Cat owners should provide their cats with toys.	REMOVED - covered (partially) by another statement, somewhat peripheral								
For little cost a garden can be made secure and become cat proof.	Gloucestershire Echo, 18/12/2012	For a little cost a garden can be made secure and cat proof.		For a little cost a garden can be made secure and cat proof.		It's straightforward to make a garden secure and cat proof	Broadened to remove cost element	It's straightforward to make a garden secure and cat proof		It's straightforward to make a garden secure and cat proof	
People may moan about cats but they help to keep the rat population down.	Birmingham Evening Mail, 10/9/2009	Cats help to keep the rat population down.	Combined with another statement -- > cats help to keep rodent populations down		REMOVED - covered by combined statement						
Not all cats hunt and those that do usually reduce their predation	Birmingham Evening Mail, 3/5/2007	Not all cats hunt.		Not all cats that go outside hunt		Not all cats that go outside hunt wild animals	Specified what is being hunted	Cats that go outside will hunt wild animals if	Inverted to make positive; specified outdoor cats	Cats that go outside will hunt wild animals if	

activity after their first three years of life.								they get the chance		they get the chance	
	Birmingham Evening Mail, 3/5/2007	Cats that hunt usually reduce their predation activity after their first three years.		Cats that hunt usually reduce their predation activity after their first three years.		Cats that hunt do so less as they get older	Simplified and broadened		REMOVED: doesn't add insight to views		
by the way, there's all this stuff that says this is not good for the cat's mental wellbeing, so it came off.	6	Collars with bells aren't good for a cat's mental wellbeing		Collars with bells aren't good for a cat's mental wellbeing		Collars with bells are bad for a cat's mental wellbeing	Inverted to make positive	Collars with bells are bad for a cat's mental wellbeing		Collars with bells are bad for a cat's mental wellbeing	
birds may be saved but mice and that, I don't see how effective that would be.	14	I don't see collars and bells as being effective			COMBINED with another statement to make "Belled collars can effectively reduce the amount of animals that cats catch"						

<p>I've spent too much money on collars because you buy them a nice collar and then within twenty minutes of them going out, they've pinged it off and you don't know where it is. I: Oh right, so you've lost collars that way. R2: I've lost so many collars, I must have spent at least sixty quid on collars for all of them.</p>	3	<p>It's too expensive to use safety collars because cats regularly lose them.</p>		<p>It's too expensive to use safety collars because cats regularly lose them.</p>		<p>I wouldn't use safety collars because cats regularly lose them</p>	<p>Removed specificity of cost; could be inconvenience</p>	<p>Quick-release collars are no use because cats regularly lose them</p>	<p>The word 'safety' could be leading - and too specific</p>	<p>Quick-release collars are no use because cats regularly lose them</p>	
								<p>Keeping cats indoors is cruel</p>	<p>ADDED: to cover range of issues about naturalness and welfare implications of keeping cats indoors</p>	<p>Keeping cats indoors is cruel</p>	
								<p>Cats should have free access to both the house and the outdoors</p>	<p>ADDED: suggestion from pilot</p>	<p>Cats should have free access to both the house and the outdoors</p>	

								Breeding of cats should be regulated	ADDED: suggestion from pilot	Breeding of cats should be regulated	
								I know what owners can do to effectively control their cat's hunting	ADDED: suggestion from pilot, modified to broader version of "I would like to reduce my cat's hunting but don't know how"	I know what owners can do to effectively control their cat's hunting	

Table S1b: Themes and sub-themes of the concourse developed for a Q-study of shooting participants on the use of lead ammunition and its impacts on wildlife and people. Statements with broad similarities were allocated to the same defined themes and sub-themes that emerged inductively from the concourse (Webler et al., 2009). It was determined that key themes had been identified when no new themes emerged (Marshall, 1999; Thompson, 2003).

Theme	Sub-theme
Evidence	Impacts of lead ammunition on wildlife Impacts of lead ammunition on human Impacts of lead ammunition on domestic animals Effectiveness of non-toxic ammunition Toxicity and pathways Communication of the evidence General over-arching statements
Mitigation	Principles of regulation Current regulations Compliance with regulations Enforcement of the regulations Total ban on lead shot Meat handling techniques (to reduce risk to humans) Remedial work (e.g. removal of top soil) Communication of the risks General over-arching statements Miscellaneous
Impacts and practicalities of mitigation	Positive Negative
Attitudes of stakeholders	Shooters Conservationists The Lead Ammunition Group Miscellaneous
Process and approach	
Social/cultural aspects	
General over-arching statements	

